

The Electronic Spectra of the Quinoline N-oxide Adduct of Oxovanadium (IV) chloride

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IN a previous communication¹, the preliminary results regarding the isolation and characterization of $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}^*$ (Found : C, 50.9; H, 3.70; N, 6.38; Cl, 16.9 and V, 12.1%; Calc. C, 50.5; H, 3.27; N, 6.54; Cl, 16.8 and V 11.9%) was reported. The compound is moderately soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, pyridine, tetrahydrofuran, acetonitrile and dichloromethane, but insoluble in chloroform, ether, benzene, light petroleum and carbon tetrachloride. It has been found that methanol solvates the species extensively and the conductance data of the said complex in methanol has been discussed elaborately elsewhere². The solvation reaction is far less in acetonitrile medium and in dichloromethane solvent the compound is practically non electrolyte.

The isolated oxovanadium (IV) complexes are mostly five coordinated and assume square pyramidal geometry^{3,4}. The complex, $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ contains only V-Cl (terminal) band⁵ (Split) at 340 cm^{-1} and there is no band in the V-Cl (bridging) region and it contains a very sharp strong V=O band⁶ at 998 cm^{-1} . These preclude the polymerisation through chlorine bridging or oxygen bridging ($\text{V}=\text{O} \dots \text{V}=\text{O} \dots$). So, the N-oxide complex may be a five co-ordinated square pyramidal species having either cis or trans configuration as depicted in Fig. 1. Since the vanadium atom

However, from the construction of models of both cis and trans form of $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ with the help of framework molecular models⁷ equipped with reasonably accurate bond lengths and atomic frames with correct van der Waals' radii, it appears that the quinoline N-oxide groups are not free to rotate when they are in the cis positions but no such restriction of rotation exists if they occupy trans positions with respect to each other. The cis compound would, therefore, be thermodynamically far less stable than the trans compound and the isolated very stable crystalline solid may have the trans configuration.

Considering that the V-O-N bonds are linear, the trans compound may possess C_{2v} symmetry and so the field created, being not much different⁸ from the C_{4v} field the ligand field spectra of the compound may be interpreted in the light of Ballhausen-Gray scheme⁹. The electronic spectral data of $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ in pyridine, methanol, acetonitrile and dichloromethane solvents are given in the Table 1. In all

TABLE I THE ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION BANDS OF $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvents	Band positions cm^{-1}	ϵ_{max}	Possible assignments ^{8,9}
Dichloromethane	14,450-14,990 24,730 (sh)	70 —	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_1 + {}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$
Acetonitrile	14,600-15,080	68	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_1 + {}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$
Methanol	13,350-13,970	28	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_1 + {}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$
Pyridine	13,350-13,700	42	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_1 + {}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$

the solvents a broad band is found in the visible region with maxima ranging from 13,350 to $15,080 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, according to the nature of the solvent

Fig. 1. Structures representing Cis and Trans configurations of the complex.

is supposed to be slightly lifted⁴ above the plane occupied by equatorial ligands it is very difficult to decide whether the isolated compound is cis or trans.

*QO = Quinoline N-oxide.

used. The nature of the band maxima suggests that at least two bands (Fig. 2) are overlapped in this region. In pyridine and methanol solvents the observed bands are at lower energy regions than those found in acetonitrile and dichloromethane (Table 1). Possibly due to the occupation in solution

of pyridine or methanol as the sixth ligand, the $O \rightarrow V$ π -bond is slightly affected making this discrimination. Only in the most non-interacting solvent as dichloromethane, the band $2B_2 \rightarrow 2A_1$ appears as a shoulder at $24,730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ being observed at the low energy tail of the U.V. bands (Fig. 2B). The pyridine solution is quite unstable and the colour of the solution gradually changes from green to yellow at room temperature and ultimately, after two days, to a deep yellow solution. No $d-d$ transition band is observed in the latter solution suggesting thereby that the oxovanadium (IV) complex is decomposed in pyridine with subsequent oxidation to vanadium (V) state. The methanol solution of the complex [where the $d-d$ band is observed in the same region as in the pyridine solvent (Table 1)] also changes colour similarly but the rate is quite slow.

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Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of the complex in the visible region :
A. In methanol
B. In dichloromethane

The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band characteristic of the N-oxide in the quinoline N-oxide molecule¹⁰ in different solvents before and after complex formation is shown in Table 2. In dichloromethane and acetonitrile solvents the hypsochromic shift characteristic of complex

TABLE 2. ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS OF $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ IN HIGH ENERGY REGION

Solvents	Band position in QO (nm)	Band position in $\text{VOCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{QO}$ (nm)	Shift (nm)
Dichloromethane	338	333	5
Acetonitrile	338	336	2
Pyridine	345	345	0
Methanol	340	340	0

formation is observed though in the latter solvent the extent of this shift is lesser. But no such shifts are observed in pyridine and methanol solvents where probably solvent interaction at such a high dilution completely decomposes the complex with the liberation of the N-oxide.

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Flavonoids of Sugar-Cane

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THE dark reddish-brown peelings of sugar-cane were extracted with boiling ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated and fractionated